

THE ROLE OF MATERIAL AND TECHNICAL SUPPLY RESOURCES IN PROVIDING QUALITY KNOWLEDGE FROM THE SCIENCE OF TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION.

G. ABDUGODIROV

associate professor of the Department of "Technological Education Methodology" of Nizomi Tashkent city Pedagogical University

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Abstract.

This article examines the role of material and technical support resources in providing quality knowledge in the field of technological education practicum.

Keywords: study; technological education provision; developed; observations; research; methodological instructions; perfect; preparation; recommendation.

Pupils acquire basic knowledge about the material and technical support of educational workshops, plan them and hand and electrical tools used in the educational workshop, machine tools, electrical and mechanized equipment, machine elements, the basics of new techniques and advanced technology, technological maps, their use, interior and equipment design; directions of modern development; preparation of schematic images and sketches of placement of furniture and additional equipment in classrooms and subject classrooms, organization of workplaces; electrical appliances; working tools should have an idea about technological documents. Currently, the need for mature personnel with innovative development and intellectual potential is increasing day by day. creates ample opportunities to find optimal solutions to problems in various directions. Only if the material and technical base of technological education is well organized, it will be possible to train qualified specialists in terms of quality. It is very difficult, and sometimes impossible, to organize a standard educational process that provides.

It belongs to the resources of material and technical support, it will have the following components:

Technology "resources of material and technical support necessary for science

1	A ruler	1 m	10 piece
		50sm	10 piece
2	Roulette	5 m	2 piece
3	Egos	Flat	30 piece
		Rough	30 piece
		Triangle	30 piece
		A rectangle	30 piece
		A semicircle	30 piece

		Round	30 piece
		Rhombic	30 piece
		Nadfil	2 komplet
4	Khatkash		30 piece
5	Angle ruler		30 piece
6	Wood		10 piece 10 piece
7	Rubber		30 piece
8	Plastic mallets		30 piece
9		Engraver	30 piece
10	Randa	Passenger	30 piece
11	Saw		5 piece
12	Iskana		2 piece
13			2 pochka
14	Warehouse		1 piece 1 piece 1 piece 1 piece
15	Mix extractor		2 piece
16	Parma (Swerlo) set		1 piece
17	Electric drill		1 piece
18	Electric range		1 piece
19	Electric saw		1 piece
20	Electric grinding machine		NS-12
21	Woodworking. Electric lathe		10 piece
22	JET (branded)		15 piece
22	Milling lathe		(1kg each)
23	Lathe lathe		(1kg each)
24	Turning lathe		0.5 kg
25	Grinding lathe		5 lists
26	Lathe		(0.5) cube

1	Ruler (metal)	1 meter	5 piece
		50 cm	10 piece
2	Roulette	5 m	2 piece
3,4	Egos	Flat	10 piece
		Rough	10 piece
		Triangle	10 piece
		A rectangle	10 piece
		A semicircle	10 piece
		Round	10 piece
		Rhombic	10 piece
		Nadfil	2 komplet
5	Micrometer		10 piece
6	Barbell circular		10 piece
7	Kerner		15 piece
8	Zubila		15 piece
9	If flat		10 piece
10	Drill kit		2 pochka
11	Electric drill		2 piece
12	Hammer	Round seal	15 piece
		A rectangle	30 piece
13	Electric lathe (JET) Metal		2 piece
14	Milling lathe		2 piece
15	Turning lathe		2 piece
16	Grinding lathe		2 piece
17	Lathe		2 piece

18	Tiskie		15 piece
19	Metal sheet (08-1) mm		10 lists
20	Scissors (Metal)		15 piece
21	Electric belt		1 piece
22	Rivet nail diameter (3, 4, 5) mm		0.5 kg
23	Rod Diameter 15 mm		50 metr

DISCUSSION: Well-equipped workshops, training grounds and training fields are expected to be organized in the workshops of enterprises and collective farms. Here, students acquire the skills of organizing a workplace, get acquainted with the mechanisms, equipment, tools and equipment necessary for the performance of work, acquire the culture of production of work methods of performing a set of operations and works in a technological order, from study time learn to use efficiently, to comply with the requirements of safety techniques, production and technological discipline.

CONCLUSION:

The presence of educational workshops creates the necessary conditions for frontal training of students. Such opportunities can be one of the fundamental didactic bases for improving the educational process, starting from the teaching of certain subjects and ending with the training of future specialists in a certain direction. In this regard, of course, in the teaching of any subject or in the preparation of modern competitive mature personnel in a voluntary direction, the state documents related to them, the demand for future specialists, and the material and technical support for carrying out activities in them. In order to pay great attention to the resources, wide opportunities have been created in our country. Based on the preparation of the complex of material and technical support resources, the role of material and technical support resources in the preparation of knowledgeable specialists is guaranteed for the quality teaching of technology.

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